

Formation of Heterocyclic Compounds from some Derivatives of Ethyl Carbazinate.

BY D. N. MAJUMDAR AND P. C. GUHA

It has been shown by Guha and Guha (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **4**, 161, 239) that dithiocarbazine ester reacts with thiocarbimides, acid chlorides, diketones etc., to give rise to interesting heterocyclic compounds. The present investigation was undertaken with a view to making a comparative study of the behaviour of some typical derivatives of ethyl carbazinate and ethyl dithiocarbazinate towards the formation of heterocyclic compounds, from which idea can be formed as to the respective influence exerted by the oxygen and the sulphur atoms in the process of ring-closure.

Ethyl carbazinate reacts with mustard oils to yield carbethoxythiosemicarbazides identical with those obtained by Fromm (*Ber.*, 1923, **56**, 1370) from thiosemicarbazides by the action of chloroformic ester.

Carbethoxythiosemicarbazides do not lend themselves to ring-closure on being merely boiled with water or alcohol as has been observed by Guha and Guha (*loc. cit.*) in the case of the corresponding thiosemicarbazide dithiocarboxylates, $\text{RNH} \cdot \text{CS} \cdot \text{NH} \cdot \text{CS} \cdot \text{SEt}$.

Compound (I) on treatment with 2 *N*-caustic potash yields by the elimination of a molecule of alcohol, a compound of the composition $\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{ON}_3\text{S}$. It melts at 283-84°. Though the compound is soluble in alkali, it cannot be desulphurised by treatment with red oxide of mercury showing the presence of the sulphur atom as a member of the ring (*cf.* Guha, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, **44**, 1502). Three compounds, A (Guha and Sen, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **4**, 44), B (Arndt, Milde, Tschenscher, *Ber.*, 1922, **55**, 341), C (Guha and Janniah, *J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1933, **16A**, 23) of this composition are already known and possess different melting points. There is,

(A, m.p. 246°)

(B, m.p. 196°)

(C, m.p. 206°)

however, another possible formula for the new compound *viz.*, 4-*N*-phenyl-3-oxy-3:5-endothio-1:2:4-triazole (II) which can be formed from the carbethoxyphenylthiosemicarbazide through the transient intermediate stages A or B as follows:

By the action of strong hydrochloric acid compound (I) loses a molecule of aniline and there is formed 3-ethoxy-5-thiol-4:1:2-oxdiazole (III).

That the sulphur atom in compound (III) is not a member of the ring is proved by its desulphurisation with red oxide of mercury; as a mercaptan it also forms a disulphide.

Carbazinic ester reacts with phenyl isocyanate to yield 4-phenylsemicarbazide-1-carboxylate (IV) which does not lend itself to any sort of ring formation though from the corresponding dithiocarboxylate Guha and Guha (*loc. cit.*) obtained 2-phenylimino-3-acetyl-5-methylthiol-2:3-dihydro-4:1:2-oxdiazole by the action of acetic anhydride.

Ethyl carbazinate reacts with carbon disulphide and alcoholic potash to yield potassium carbethoxydithiocarbazinate which, with methyl iodide gives methyl carbethoxydithiocarbazinate (V) thus:

The correctness of the structure of compound (V) has been established by its synthesis from ethyl chlorocarbonate and methyl dithiocarbazinate.

The action of mono- and dialdehydes on ethyl carbazinate proceeds in the normal way yielding the corresponding carbethoxy hydrazones ;

Guha and De (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 2, 228) obtained closed ring thiocarbohydrazones from thiocarbohydrazide and *o*-diktones, similar participation of both of the keto groups of *o*-diketones in their reaction with methyl dithiocarbazinate to form oxdiazine rings has been observed by Guha and Guha (*loc. cit.*). Ethyl carbazinate reacts, however, with only one of the ketonic groups of the diketones to form the monocarbethoxyhydrazones (VIII)

Carbonyl and oxalyl chlorides yield carbodicarbazinic ester (IX) and oxalyldicarbazinic ester (X) respectively, and not any ring compound as was the case with methyl dithiocarbazinate in its reaction with diacid chlorides (Guha and Guha, *loc. cit.*, p. 241).

Phthalyl chloride reacts with carbazinic ester to yield a compound $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2$ which though stable towards boiling water is decomposed into phthalic acid and carbazinic ester when heated with strong hydrochloric acid. Of the four possible formulæ (XIa, XIb,

(XIa)

(XIb)

(XIc)

(XI d)

XIc, XI d), (XIc) and (XI d) necessitate the α -iminohydrogen of the carbazinic esters to participate in ring formation which from a consideration of the general inertness observed in other reactions, does not seem to be very likely; besides a compound of formula (XI d) possessing an eight-membered ring with the grouping CO·O·CO present in it cannot be expected to be stable.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Ethyl carbazinate was prepared according to the method of Theile and Lachmann (*Annalen*, 1895, 288, 267) modified as follows: The benzaldehyde compound of the crude carbazinic ester was hydrolysed with concentrated hydrochloric acid by heating carefully and the resulting solution extracted with hot benzene. The acid solution was evaporated on a water-bath almost to dryness and the separated light yellow needles of the hydrochloride dried in vacuum over soda lime and concentrated sulphuric acid.

Ethyl 4-phenylthiosemicarbazide-1-carboxylate (I).—Ethyl carbazinate hydrochloride (5.2 g.) dissolved in alcohol (50 c.c.) was slowly added to a mixture of phenylmustard oil (5 g.) and anhydrous sodium carbonate (3.9 g.) dissolved in minimum quantity of water and the mixture heated under reflux during 3 hours on a water-bath. The alcoholic solution was filtered off from the precipitated sodium chloride and the filtrate concentrated to a small bulk. On cooling a quantity of oily substance settled at the bottom which soon solidified. This after being freed from unreacted carbazinic ester crystallised from alcohol in needles, m.p. 141-42°. It is soluble in dilute alkali. (Found: N, 17.51. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2\text{S}$ requires N, 17.57 per cent).

4-Phenylimino-3-hydroxy-3:5-endothio-2:3-dihydro-1:3:4-triazole (II).—Carbethoxyphenylthiosemicarbazide (2 g.) dissolved in excess of 2N-KOH solution was heated under reflux on a sand-bath during 4 hours. The solution after acidification with dilute hydrochloric acid

was concentrated to a small volume and potassium chloride precipitated by alcohol filtered off. The filtrate on concentration and cooling gave a solid which crystallised from alcohol in fine white needles, m.p. 283-84° (decomp.) It is soluble in dilute alkali and remained unchanged on mercuric oxide treatment. (Found: N, 21.15. $C_8H_7ON_3S$ requires N, 21.24 per cent).

3-Ethoxy-5-thiol-4:1:2-oxdiazole (III).—Carbethoxysphenylthiosemicarbazide (2 g.) was boiled under reflux with concentrated hydrochloric acid (50 c.c.) for 2 hours. The excess of acid was nearly neutralised with dilute sodium hydroxide and the solution concentrated to a smaller bulk and the sodium chloride precipitated by alcohol filtered off. The filtrate was evaporated to dryness and the residue crystallised from alcohol in fine microscopic needles, m.p. 274-75° (decomp.). It is soluble in alkali, yields a disulphide with iodine and can easily be desulphurised by red oxide of mercury. (Found: N, 19.01. $C_4H_6O_2N_2S$ requires N, 19.1 per cent).

4-Phenylsemicarbazide-1-carboxylate (IV).—To ethyl carbazinate generated from the hydrochloride (2.4 g.) was added phenylisocyanate (2 g.) gradually with constant shaking and the mixture heated under reflux for 15 minutes on a water-bath and filtered hot. The filtrate on dilution with water gave a brownish oil which soon solidified. It was then powdered and shaken repeatedly with ether to remove diphenylcarbamide formed by the action of water on the isocyanate. The ether insoluble residue after being washed with dilute hydrochloric acid and water was crystallised from alcohol in prisms, m.p. 154-55°. It is insoluble in alkali. (Found: N, 19.84. $C_{10}H_{11}O_2N_3$ requires N, 20.48 per cent).

Methyl carbethoxydithiocarbazinate (V).—Ethyl carbazinate hydrochloride (2.8 g.) and carbon disulphide (1.5 g.) were taken in a flask together with alcohol sufficient to dissolve the hydrochloride. To that an alcoholic solution of potassium hydroxide (1.1 g.) was added gradually under shaking and the mixture gently warmed on a water-bath. After cooling, methyl iodide (4.0 g.) was added and the reaction mixture after standing for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour was poured into water and extracted with ether, the extract shaken several times with dilute hydrochloric acid and then with water. After removal of ether, the residue was crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 90-91°. (Found: N, 14.35. $C_5H_{10}O_2N_2S_2$ requires N, 14.4 per cent).

Compound (V) was also prepared by the action of chloroacetic ester on methyl dithiocarbazinate prepared according to the method

of Busch (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1916, **93**, 59). It had m.p. 90-91° which remained undepressed on admixture with a sample prepared by the foregoing method.

Ethyl o-nitrobenzylidenecarbazinate (VI, R = *o*-C₆H₄·NO₂).—To an alcoholic solution of *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde (2.8 g.) and ethyl carbazinate hydrochloride (3 g.) was added an aqueous solution of anhydrous sodium carbonate (3.25 g.) and the mixture heated under reflux for ½ hour on a water-bath. The solution was filtered off from the precipitated sodium chloride and the filtrate on concentration and cooling gave a crystalline solid which after being washed with dilute acid and water was recrystallised in light yellow needles from alcohol, m.p. 130-31°. (Found: N, 18.4. C₁₀H₁₂O₄N₃ requires N, 18.65 per cent).

Ethyl salicylidenecarbazinate (VI, R = C₆H₄OH) crystallised from alcohol in plates, m.p. 129-30°. (Found: N, 13.39. C₁₀H₁₂O₃N₂ requires N, 13.46 per cent).

Ethyl p-tolylidenecarbazinate [VI, R = C₆H₄CH₃, (*p*)] crystallised from alcohol in light yellow needles, m.p. 116-18°. (Found: N, 13.42. C₁₁H₁₄O₂N₂ requires N, 13.39 per cent).

Ethyl cinnamylidenecarbazinate (VI, R = C₆H₅CH:CH) crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 196-97°. (Found: N, 12.78. C₁₂H₁₄O₂N₂ requires N, 12.84 per cent).

Ethyl piperonylidenecarbazinate (VI, R = CH₂O₂·C₆H₃) crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 123-24.5°. (Found: N, 12.0. C₁₁H₁₂O₄N₂ requires N, 11.87 per cent).

Ethyl furfurylidenecarbazinate (VI, R = C₄H₃O) crystallised from alcohol in light brown needles, m.p. 132.5-33.5°. (Found: N, 15.29. C₈H₁₀O₃N₂ requires N, 15.38 per cent).

Ethyl vanilinidenecarbazinate [VI, R = C₆H₃(OCH₃) OH (3:1)] crystallised from alcohol in light brown needles, m.p. 152.5-53.5°. (Found: N, 11.69. C₁₁H₁₄O₄N₂ requires N, 11.77 per cent).

Ethyl glyoxylicdicarbazinate (VII).—Ethyl carbazinate hydrochloride (2 g.) and sodium glyoxal bisulphite (1.82 g.) were dissolved in water and heated on a water-bath for 1 hour, when a white precipitate separated which being insoluble in ordinary organic solvents could not be crystallised. It was boiled with alcohol and dried at 100°, m.p. 305-06° (decomp.). (Found: N, 28.58. C₈H₁₄O₄N₄ requires N, 28.69 per cent).

Camphorquinone monocarbethoxyhydrazone (VIII).—To an alcoholic solution of camphorquinone (1.18 g.) and ethyl carbazinate

hydrochloride (1 g.) was added an aqueous solution of anhydrous sodium carbonate (0.75 g.) and the mixture heated under reflux for 8 hours on a water-bath. The filtered solution was concentrated almost to dryness and the sodium chloride removed after precipitation with absolute alcohol. The filtrate on concentration and cooling gave a crystalline solid which after being washed with ether was recrystallised from alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 199.5-200°. (Found: C, 62.1; H, 8.34; N, 11.02. $C_{13}H_{20}O_3N_2$ requires C, 61.9; H, 7.93; N, 11.19 per cent).

Phenanthraquinone monocarbethoxyhydrazone.—An aqueous alcoholic solution of phenanthraquinone (2.9 g.), ethyl carbazinate hydrochloride (2.0 g.) and anhydrous sodium carbonate (1.5 g.) was heated under reflux for 8 hours on a water-bath and the separated solid after being shaken with hot benzene, was washed with dilute acid and then with water. It is insoluble in all the ordinary organic solvents and could only be obtained as a brown amorphous powder from pyridine, m.p. above 320° after softening at 275°. (Found: N, 9.3. $C_{17}H_{14}O_3N_2$ requires N, 9.53 per cent).

Acetophenone carbethoxyhydrazone [C (PhMe)=N·NH·CO₂Et].—It was prepared by a process similar to that adopted from the preparation of the foregoing compound and was crystallised from alcohol in fine colourless needles, m.p. 119.6-20.6°. (Found: N, 13.41. $C_{11}H_{14}O_2N_2$ requires N, 13.59 per cent).

Carbodicarbazine ester (IX).—A mixture of carbonyl chloride (5 c.c. of 20% solution in toluene), ethyl carbazinate hydrochloride (2.0 g.) and anhydrous sodium carbonate (0.8 g.) in dry benzene (20 c.c.) was heated under reflux for 3 hours on a water-bath. The contents of the flask were filtered and the filtrate evaporated to dryness, the residue crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 119-20°. (Found: N, 23.75. $C_7H_{14}O_5N_4$ requires N, 23.9 per cent).

Oxalyldicarbazine ester (X).—The compound was obtained by the above process using oxalyl chloride and was crystallised from alcohol in colourless plates, m.p. 182-83° (decomp.). (Found: N, 21.08. $C_8H_{14}O_6N_4$ requires N, 21.37 per cent).

o-Phthalalyldicarbazine ester (XI).—A mixture of phthalyl chloride (2.9 g.), ethyl carbazinate hydrochloride (2.0 g.) and anhydrous sodium carbonate (2.5 g.) in dry benzene was heated under reflux for about 1 hour on a water-bath. The contents of the flask were filtered off from the separated sodium chloride and the filtrate

evaporated to dryness. The residue was shaken with a solution of sodium bicarbonate to remove phthalic acid formed during the reaction and some unreacted phthalyl chloride washed with dilute acid and water and crystallised from alcohol in fine colourless needles, m.p. 166-67°. It is soluble in cold alkali and is decomposed by boiling concentrated hydrochloric acid into ethyl carbazinate and phthalic acid. (Found: N, 12.25. $C_{11}H_{10}O_4N_2$ requires N, 12.0 per cent).

Action of ethyl chlorocarbonate upon ethyl carbazinate: formation of ethyl hydrazinedicarboxylic ester.—To a mixture of an alcoholic solution of ethyl carbazinate hydrochloride (2.0 g.) and an aqueous solution of sodium carbonate (0.8 g.), chlorocarbonic ester (2 g.) was gradually added with constant stirring. The mixture was warmed on a water-bath for about an hour and the separated sodium chloride filtered off. The filtrate gave on concentration and cooling a solid which crystallised from alcohol in needles, m.p. 131.5-32.5°. (Found: N, 15.8. $C_6H_{12}O_4N_2$ requires N, 15.9 per cent).

DEPARTMENT OF ORGANIC CHEMISTRY,
INDIAN INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE,
BANGALORE.

Received September 11, 1933.

A note of correction.—The compound described in this journal (1928, 5, 163) as 2-phenylhydrazino-1:3:4-thiodiazole was prepared in this laboratory in connection with some other work and was found to contain N, 26.34 and S, 15.20 (not 16.92 as reported before) agreeing with the composition $C_8H_{10}ON_4S$ which fits in well with the formula of formylphenylthiocarbohydrazide, $PhNH \cdot NH \cdot CS \cdot NH \cdot NH \cdot CHO$.